

turned into the color of clotted blood. Rice varieties could not be graded on panicle infection.

Germination and seedling vigor of discolored and healthy grains of 4 selected varieties were tested in petri plates at 30± 1°C. Varieties differed in reduction of percent germination and

root and shoot length (Table 1). Reduction was maximum in RP2151-76-1 and minimum in RP2151-27-1. Although germination in discolored seeds of Palman 579 was not affected, root length reduction was noticed.

Affected and healthy panicles from six plots of Jaya and Pusa 2-21 were

collected to study the effect of SBL on yield parameters. Number of filled grains was reduced and number of unfilled and discolored grains was higher in affected panicles (Table 2). Infection was more pronounced on Pusa 2-21 than on Jaya. □

Effect of *Azolla bipinnata* soil amendment on reduction in viability of sclerotia of rice stem rot (SR) fungus

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A greenhouse pot experiment examined the effect of *Azolla bipinnata* used as an organic substrate on the survival of sclerotia of the SR fungus *Sclerotium oryzae*. Soil artificially infested with sclerotia of *S. oryzae* at 5 sclerotia/g of soil was amended with fresh azolla at 0, 0.1, 0.5, and 1% wt/ wt. The soil in 7-cm-diameter pots was adjusted and maintained at 50, 75, and 100% moisture-holding capacity by watering daily. At 0, 10-, 20-, 40-, and 80-d intervals, sclerotia were separated by wet sieving and their viability tested on water agar supplemented with streptomycin sulfate and penicillin at

Table 1. Reduction in viability of sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae* in soil amended with *Azolla bipinnata* at different moisture levels. Karachi, Pakistan.

<i>Azolla</i> treatment	Moisture (%)	Reduction in viability ^a (%)			
		10 d	20 d	40 d	80 d
Control	50	4	3	3	0
	75	5	4	8	4
	100	0	10	13	13
<i>Azolla</i> 0.1%	50	10	3	9	5
	75	0	14	8	13
	100	14	13	4	17
<i>Azolla</i> 0.5%	50	4	12	8	25
	75	12	0	13	14
	100	5	8	17	35
<i>Azolla</i> 1.0%	50	1	18	5	29
	75	13	8	13	18
	100	12	16	14	26

^a Zero reduction at 0 d.

Table 2. Analysis of variance for the viability of sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae*.

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F ratio
Treatments (T)	1045.511	3	348.50	3.82**
Moisture (M)	625.328	2	312.69	3.43*
Time (D)	4220.755	4	1055.19	11.58**
TXM	306.911	6	51.15	0.56
TXD	1152.045	12	96.00	1.05
MXD	670.128	8	83.77	0.92
TXMXD	1853.533	24	77.23	0.85
Residual	10938.667	120	91.15	
Total	20812.978	179		

*P<0.05

**P<0.01

3,000 ppm each.

Maximum reduction, up to 35%, in sclerotial viability was observed with azolla at 0.5% wt/ wt (Table 1).

Azolla at different concentrations and at different time intervals showed significant reduction in viability of sclerotia (Table 2). Moisture also was significant. Interactions among

amendment, moisture, and time were not significant. Presumably soil incorporation of azolla and the decomposition of organic matter generate anaerobic conditions and/ or accumulation of fungitoxic substances due to increased microbial activity, resulting in a reduction in viability of *S. oryzae* sclerotia. □

Pestalotia oryzae - a new rice fungus in India

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A severe glume spot disease of rice was found in Manipur for the first time in 1985-86.

Symptoms appeared first as small, pale brown spots which gradually increased to 2 mm in size. The center of the spot is gray-brown with a dark brown margin and bears minute fruiting bodies of the fungus.

Diseased grains were collected in separate bags from different rice-growing valley areas during the crop season. The causal organism was isolated and maintained on potato

Panicle stage and susceptibility to *Pestalotia oryzae*. Iroisemba, Manipur, India, 1985-86.

Panicle stage	Panicles inoculated (no.)	Panicles infected (no.)
Just emerged	30	2
Milk	30	30
Dough	30	6
Mature	30	0

dextrose agar (PDA) medium. Pathogenicity of the fungus was proved by inoculating young panicles with 7-d-old cultures.

The fungus failed to infect the living leaves. However, it could easily infect dead rice leaves.

The isolated pathogenic fungus has been identified as *Pestalotia oryzae* Hara. This is the first record of its

occurrence on rice glumes in India.

The fungus produces hyaline, caenocytic mycelium. Conidiophores are short and simple. Conidia are dark and 5-celled, with hyaline and pointed-end

cells having 2–3 hyaline apical appendages. Size of conidia is 30–35 × 7–10 µm with appendages 20–35 µm long.

During pathogenicity tests, mycelial

bits of the fungus were prepared from 7-d-old culture and sprayed on rice grain at different stages. The milk stage was found to be most susceptible to fungal infection (see table). □

Effect of grain spotting on rice quality

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Grain spotting is caused by several microorganisms (*Trichoconis* spp., *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Pyricularia oryzae*, *Aspergillus* spp., *Alternaria padwickii*, *Curvularia* spp., etc.).

Symptoms (distinct black dots, sometimes brown blackish blotches) vary with the degree of infection.

We sampled grain lots of 21 varieties and measured grain spotting incidence.

Twenty-five healthy and 25 infected seeds of each variety were selected at random, dehusked, and the husk and grain weighed.

Ten healthy and 10 infected seeds were dehusked and the grains placed in 15- × 1-cm test tubes with 10 ml water each tube. Grain volume was measured. The tubes were placed in a 500-ml beaker with 200 ml water, heated for 30

Loss to grain spotting, Bilaspur, India.

Variety	Infection (%)	Loss (g) in husk weight	Difference in 1000-grain weight (g)	Cooking expansion difference (ml)
Jaya	6.2	0.26	1.79	0.12
Ratna	7.3	0.18	3.27	0.12
Bd 200	3.4	0.11	2.01	0.00
R-35-2752	9.1	0.51	0.78	2.19
BPT1235	6.2	0.31	4.33	1.95
Surekha	4.6	0.21	1.80	0.48
RP9-4	5.4	0.12	2.84	0.24
Saket-4	5.8	0.30	3.62	1.09
IR36	10.3	0.30	0.26	0.73
Chatri	10.4	0.53	0.07	1.09
Mahsuri	1.6	0.11	3.44	0.36
IET4094	5.2	0.28	5.96	1.09
R-2384	11.7	0.06	3.94	0.36
Phalguna	4.1	0.13	3.75	0.45
Pankaj	4.0	0.10	2.09	0.00
Kranti	6.9	0.17	0.20	0.61
Pusa	7.3	0.11	3.99	0.61
IET3273	11.5	0.39	0.65	0.36
Jagriti	4.7	0.27	1.70	0.24
Garima	4.5	0.12	1.86	0.36
Patel 85	4.8	0.21	2.73	0.73

min, and grain volume after cooking measured.

All varieties showed grain spotting (see table). Infected seeds weighed less

than healthy seeds. Infected husk also weighed less. Healthy grains expanded more than spotted grains with cooking. □

Distribution of rice seedling damping-off in Bangladesh

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Rice seedling damping-off caused by *Achlya* sp. was first identified in Bangladesh in 1978. The disease is soil borne and is disseminated through both soil and water. The pathogen affects seeds or young seedlings during the winter (Nov–Feb). The fungus forms a gray/ brown/ black-colored tangled mass of hyphae covering the surface of the infected seeds.

During 1978, severe seed or seedling damage occurred in the seedbed at the BRRI farm. Almost all rice varieties or

Severity of rice seedling damping-off in 11 districts of Bangladesh, winter, 1987.

District	Seedbeds affected (%)	Severity (0-9 scale ^a)
Bogra	30	5–7
Comilla	25	5–7
Chittagong	25	5–7
Dinajpur	40	5–7
Gazipur	30	5–9
Jamalpur	70	5–9
Mymensingh	30	5–7
Pabna	30	5–7
Rajshahi	40	3–5
Rangpur	60	3–9
Tangail	20	3–5

^a 0 = no incidence, 3 = 11–20% damage, 4 = 21–30% damage, 5 = 31–40% damage, 6 = 41–50% damage, 7 = 51–60% damage, 8 = 61–70% damage, and 9 = 81–100% damage.

lines sown were affected, with up to 80% seed or seedling mortality.

We surveyed the distribution and intensity of the disease in different districts during Jan 1987. The disease was prevalent in all 11 districts visited, with damage as high as 70% in seedbeds kept submerged during and after sowing (see table). □

Relationship between tungro transmission by individual *Nephotettix virescens*, mode of feeding, and life span

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A green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* colony collected from